

QUIZ**LAST NAME: AINSWORTH****FIRST NAME: ODGEREL****PROGRAM CODE: MSDD****COURSE CODE : ACA-401****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA**

The quiz uses US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.
The Rule of Style is Turabian (footnotes).

QUIZ

1. What is the purpose of citation?¹

- To remind you who the author is.
- To give credit to the source used in-text.**
- There is no significant purpose.
- All of the above is correct.

2. Plagiarism is ...²

- Acceptable when it is unintentional.
- Acceptable when if the source gave you permission.
- Never acceptable in any form.**
- Acceptable when you think it is ok.

3. Which of the following is correct?³

¹ Euclid University, *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 1* (Washington DC: Euclid University Press, 2015), 9.

² Ibid.,8.

- In US style, punctuation should be placed inside of the quotation mark.**
 - Only UK style allows you to use punctuation inside of the quotation mark.
 - Both US and UK styles allow you to use punctuation outside of the quotation mark.
 - Both US and UK styles allow you to use punctuation inside of the quotation mark.
4. **Turabian manual describes which two citations?⁴**
- Author-date style and Notes-bibliography style.**
 - Author-note style and Title-bibliography style.
 - Notes-citation style and Author-date style.
 - Title-date style and Notes-bibliography style
5. **When citing in-text in author-date style, what is the basic form?⁵**
- Author's Last Name, First Name, Year of Publication, Page Number.
 - Author's First Name, Last Name, Year of Publication, Page Number.
 - Author's Last Name, First Name, Page Number.
 - Author's Last Name, Year of Publication, Page Number.**
6. **Which of the most appropriate way to reduce writing errors in you paper?⁶**
- Submit and wait feedback.
 - Utilize spelling and review option in word.**

³ Euclid University, *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 1* (Washington DC: Euclid University Press, 2015), 6.

⁴ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style of Students and Researchers*, 8th ed (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 87

⁵ Ibid., 129

⁶ Ibid.

- Utilize word-count and word-index in word.
- Read over and over the document.

7. **The main purpose of an expository essay is?**⁷

- To change the audience's position.
- To explain a topic in a logical and straightforward manner.**
- Have a platform to give an opinion without facts.
- Attempt to get the reader to agree with your point of view.

8. **Where in a word is the suffix found?**⁸

- The middle.
- The front.
- The end.**
- Wherever the most meaning is.

9. **Compare the words 'assist' to 'assistance.' The addition of the suffix '-ance' does what?**⁹

- Lengthens the word.
- Makes the writer look smart.
- Turns a noun into a plural noun.
- Turns a verb into a noun.**

⁷ Patrick Sebranek, Dave Kemper, and Verne Meyer, *Write Source 2000: A Guide to Writing, Thinking, and Learning* (Massachusetts: a Houghton Mifflin Company, 1999), 107-110.

⁸ Ibid.,331.

⁹ Ibid.

10. Which of the following are the examples of TRUNCATION?¹⁰

- Feb, Tues, St.
- Mr, Dr.
- BBC, USA
- AIDS, NASA, and NATO.

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¹⁰ European Commission, *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*, 7th ed (Brussels: European Union Press, 2011), 27.